

ISic1631

Epitaph for Ianouarios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.01.17

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Contrada Murica

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Archeologico Gabriele Judica, inventory 2245

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175472

1. Ἰανουάριος ἐνθάδε κίτε ζήσας χρηστῶς καὶ ἀμένπτως ἔτ [η---]

2. καὶ ἐν Λογαριανοῖς πρεσβύτερος ἔτη μ' καὶ δ'

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645082

PHI 175472

Bibliography

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